

Supporting Information: Simulation of the Carbon Dioxide Hydrate-Water Interfacial Energy

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According to the main article, we have determined the time evolution of n_h , the number of water molecules in the CO₂ hydrate slab, for eighteen different well radii, ranging from 0.76 (0.24 σ) to 1.457 Å (0.46 σ), with $\sigma = 3.1668$ Å the diameter associated with the Lennard-Jones intermolecular potential of the TIP4P/ice model of water. All the results are presented in Figures S1, S2, and S3. As it is explained in the main paper, it is possible to identify three different scenarios:

(a) Scenario I, corresponding to systems with $r_w \leq 1.172$ Å (0.37 σ) in which none of the trajectories exhibits induction period and system always crystallizes if simulation runs are sufficiently long (no free energy barrier between the fluid and solid phases exists), see Figure S1.

(b) Scenario II, corresponding to intermediate values with 1.203 Å $\leq r_w \leq 1.283$ Å (0.38 $\sigma \leq r_w \leq 0.405\sigma$) in which at least one trajectory shows an induction period, i.e., n_h does not grow, on average, from $t=0$ ns, see Figure S2. Particularly, different induction periods can be observed for systems with $r_w = 1.203$ (0-30 ns for orange and green trajectories), 1.219 (0-30 ns for blue trajectory and 0-70 ns for orange trajectory), 1.235 (0-10 ns for orange, 0-15 ns for maroon, and 0-20 ns for blue trajectories), 1.267 (0-40 ns for red, 0-55 ns for green, and 0-65 ns for orange trajectories), and 1.283 Å (0-45 ns for green trajectory). The common behavior of these systems, according to scenario II, is that all trajectories exhibit, on average, a monotonous growing of n_h with time, indicating that although systems have free energy barriers between the liquid and solid phases, they are able to overcome them and crystallize if simulations are long enough.

(c) Scenario III, corresponding to systems with $r_w \geq 1.298$ Å ($r_w \geq 0.41\sigma$) in which none of them exhibit, on average, monotonic increasing of n_h with time due to the existence of a free energy barrier between the fluid and solid that does not allow the system to crystallize, see Figure S3.

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Figure S1: Number of water molecules in the crystal slab, n_h , as function of time for several trajectories and different well radius, r_w (as indicated in the legend). All simulations are performed at coexistence conditions (40MPa and 287K). In all cases, $\varepsilon = 8 k_B T$. Each color represents an independent trajectory generated using different seeds starting from the same fluid configuration.

Figure S2: The conditions and meaning of the curves are the same as in Figure S1.

Figure S3: The conditions and meaning of the curves are the same as in Figure S1.